

Impediments to Female Sports Management and Participation: The Experience in the Selected Nigeria South West Colleges of Education

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Abstract—The study was meant to identify the impediments to female sports management and participation in the selected colleges. Seven colleges of education in the south west parts of the country were selected for the study. A total of one hundred and five subjects were sampled to supply data. Only one hundred adequately completed and returned, copies of the questionnaire were used for data analysis. The collected data were analysed descriptively. The result of the study showed that inadequate fund, personnel, facilities equipment, supplies, management of sports, supervision and coaching were some of the impediments to female sports management and participation. Athletes were not encouraged to participate. Based on the findings, it was recommended that the government should come to the aid of the colleges by providing fund and other needs that will make sports attractive for enhanced participation.

Keywords—Female sports, impediments, management, Nigeria, south west, colleges.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the olden days, ignorance, sexist attitudes and practices in sports have affected the participation of women in sports for many years. According to [5] for instance, in 776 B.C., women in Greece were denied the opportunity of either watching or participating in the ancient Olympic Games. Related to this is the comment of [3] that women's participation in sports has for long been a continuing struggle which from all available evidences remains an unresolved problem.

Reference [1] quotes Coubertin as saying that; "Women have but one task that of crowning the men with garlands as was their role in ancient Greece". He added that the greatest accomplishment of Women in sports was to encourage her son to excel rather than seek records for herself.

Women have never been expected to participate in any vigorous activities. Traditionally, women have always been regarded as the weaker sex, whose natural charm, beauty and femininity may be destroyed by participation in vigorous physical activity. It is, however, interesting to note that things have changed for better in this regard. This development led to the views of [3] that;

"The sports world that was formerly men's domain is now being shared with female because the myth surround

the supremacy of sports participation by men and the discrimination against women has since long broken."

With these background statements, the participation of female in sports as well as the management of their sports would have had problems. Experience has shown that administering sports in a developing country is hectic. This is so because several factors required in order to successfully manage sports may be absent. The personnel, finance, programme, facilities, equipment and supplies interest support and encouragement for instance may be lacking or deficient. These must be provided adequately if the desired result must be achieved.

Reference [6] opines that an abundant sport labour force, that is knowledgeable about the intricacies and specialties of organizing and administering sports programmes, as well as capable of instructing beginners in the fundamental skills needed for participation in sports considered a basic requirement for initiating and sustaining effective mass sports programmes in any developing country.

Expectation is very high from our sportsmen and women in our higher institutions. This point is emphasized in his speech at the University of Jos's Annual Sports and culture, Gbenga Elegbeleye, the Director, National Sport Commission remarked that;

"Nigerian University have failed the Nation in producing accomplished high performance Sportsmen and women. Other developed countries have proved that academic pursuits are not antithetical with sporting pursuits."

In his contribution to [7] opines that the nation at large expects the high institutions to provide the bulk of the Sportsmen Sportswomen who will represent her at the various international Sports Competitions. He explained further that their expectations are buttressed by the fact that the competitors from those nations that have excelled in World Sports such as the United State of America, Britain, the Germanies and Russia have been drawn largely from their higher institutions. These situations are so because of wrong institutional policies, lack of essential needs as well as wrong attitudes of members of the institutional community. It is sad to note that higher institutions in the country, South Western part of Nigeria in participation have not for a long time regarded sports as an integral part of the total education system.

Reference [9] lamented this abnormality and points out that student athlete in higher institutions in the country are not

encouraged to excel in sports. In the same vein,[4] shares similar views and adds that some lecturers discourage and frustrate the sports efforts and interests of student athletes in our higher institution.

Interestingly, several benefits are derived from sports participation. Contemporary literature in the field of physical education and sports supports the fact that active and regular participation in sports promotes the physical well-being as well as the full and well-balanced development of individuals. It is nurtured and developed in the school as a voluntary educational programme to promote health and most importantly, bring international prestige and recognition to the nation.

A. Statement of Problem

Benefits derive from good management and effective participation in sports by Sportsmen and women in Colleges of Education in South Western part of Nigeria notwithstanding, experience and literature [1], [3]-[5] have shown that problems abound in these areas. There is the need to identify the specific problems that is believed to be a worthwhile initial step towards findings solution to problems. This study will therefore find answer to this research question: what are the barriers to female sports management and participation in the selected College of Education in the South Western part of Nigeria.

B. Methods and Procedure

1. Population and Sample

The population and Sample of both of government and private colleges of Education in the Western part of Nigeria; fifteen were selected in such a way that the various major parts of the zone were represented.

At each of these institutions, twenty sports women were randomly selected to complete the questionnaire along with the sports Director/head of Department and four coaches/lecturers that handled the athletes. This made it a total of twenty-five per institution and an overall total of three hundred and seventy-five samples. The names are as follows:

- Osun College of Education, Ilesa
- St. Andrew College of Education, Oyo
- Federal College of Education, Osi-Ele
- Adeniran Ogunsanya College of Education, Otto, Ijanikin
- Adeyemi College of Education Ondo
- Ekiti State College of Education, Ikare-Ekiti
- Michael Otedola College of Primary Education, Noforija – Epe

C. Instrumentation

The main instrument of the study was a personally developed questionnaire which was developed upon by three colleague experienced researchers. The instrument was validated in a trial test with twenty subjects at Federal College of Education Okenne; this trial institution was not part of area where the research was conducted. The split half method of finding the reliability of test instrument was applied. A reliability co-efficient of .85 was calculated.

D. Data Collection and Analysis

With the assistance of colleagues, students and personal efforts, all copies of the questionnaire were administered; this was achieved through sending the instrument to the institutions. Out of three hundred and seventy-five copies of the questionnaire administered, only three hundred of these were found properly completed. They were therefore used for the analysis that was descriptive due to the nature of the study. The responses were tabulated in percentages as shown in the two tables of the report.

II. RESULTS

Tables I and II show the results of the study.

TABLE I
PERCENTAGE DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONSES ON IDENTIFIED IMPEDIMENTS TO FEMALE SPORTS MANAGEMENT AND PARTICIPATION IN THE SOUTH WEST OF NIGERIA COLLEGES OF EDUCATION

S/N	Variables Pertaining to Female Sports	Yes	%	No	%
1	Is sufficient fund provided?	120	40	180	60
2	Are qualified personnel employed?	160	53.3	140	46.7
3	Have you sufficient number of personnel?	165	65	135	45.7
4	Is the programme thoroughly supervised?	150	50	150	50
5	Is the sports programme well managed?	140	46.7	160	53.3
6	Are the athletes coached regularly?	80	26.7	220	73.3
7	Are your sports considered part of academic system?	22	7.3	278	92.8
8	Has the sport programme varied events?	140	46.7	160	53.3
9	Does the College Authority favour sports participation?	60	20	240	80
10	Are goof sportswomen favoured where they miss minimum qualification for admission?	15	5	285	95
11	Are sufficient facilities provided?	105	35	195	65
12	Are free hours given for sports practices?	100	33.3	200	66.7
13	Are adequate equipment and supplies available?	80	26.7	220	73.3
14	Does religion hinder sport participation?	245	81.7	55	18.3
15	Is the programme adequately publicized?	140	46.7	160	53.3
16	Do the family members hinder participation?	220	73.3	80	26.7
17	Do peers and friends constitute barrier?	240	80	60	20
18	Are sportswomen given special hall accommodation?	20	6.7	280	94.3
19	Are they given sports dinner/award night?	10	3.3	290	96.7
20	Are worthy sportswomen given scholarship?	12	4	288	96
21	Are sportswomen discouraged by lecturers	250	83.3	50	16.7

Table I shows the view of the samples on the variable pertaining to female sports management and participation in their colleges. Their responses reflect the status of the factors at each of the Colleges. These indicated that all the variables were impediments to female sports management and participation at the Colleges of Education. Some of the variables however received very high percentage of negative response, for instance, the statement on admission policy to sportswomen, provision of special hall accommodation, scholarship for sportswomen, and sports dinners. Most of these were said to be virtually absent and were impediments to female sports management and practices in the Colleges of Education.

Table II ranks the identified impediment from 1st to 21st according to the tabulated response in percentages.

TABLE II
LISTING OF IDENTIFIED IMPEDIMENTS TO FEMALE SPORTS MANAGEMENT AND PARTICIPATION IN THE ORDER OF IMPORTANCE ACCORDING TO RESPONSE

Position	Variables	%
1 st	Non-provision of sports dinner/award night	96.7
2 nd	Refusal to give sportswomen scholarship	96
3 rd	Sportsmen were denied special admission favour	95
4 th	Lack of special sportswomen hall for accommodation	93.3
5 th	Sports are not considered part of academic system	92.7
6 th	Some lecturers discourage sportswomen	83.3
7 th	Religion hinders sports participation	81.7
8 th	Peer and friends constitute barrier	80
8 th	College authority does not fully favour sports	80
10 th	Athletes are not coached regularly	73.3
10 th	Provision of inadequate equipment and supplies	73.3
10 th	Family member hinder participation	73.3
13 th	Lecture free hours are not adequately provided	66.7
14 th	Insufficient facilities are provided	65
15 th	Inadequate fund is provided	60
16 th	There was insufficient personnel	55
17 th	Personnel was not adequately qualified	53.3
17 th	Programme was not adequately publicized	53.3
17 th	Sport was not well managed	53.3
17 th	Programme not adequately varied	53.3
21 st	Programme was not thoroughly supervised	50

III. DISCUSSION FOR FINDINGS

Inadequate provision of funds was identified as an impediment to female sports management and participation in the College. It perhaps the most important factor in the execution of sports programmes. No sports director, coach or athletes can be successful without availability of funds. Another identified impediment which was easily linked with the availability of fund is personnel. Without funds, personnel cannot be adequately recruited. The issue of adequate number of personnel is different from the quality of staff. Both are however essential ingredients in sports management and participation. Defective supervision, management of the sport programme and coaching all bother on the quality of personnel.

The idea of not making sports part of the academic system is a strong impediment. According to [2] he opines that it is sad that higher institutions in the country failed to make sports an integral part of the University to produce top performer athletes. He add that it was not that potential are not in the University but they do not receive the maximum cooperation of their institutions so they cannot perform at their best. Training consumes a lot of time just as studies do. The University athlete is therefore forced to share its time for sports and academic demands. A number of factors were also found to be either absent or inadequate. The facilities, equipment, supplies and publicity were deficient. These were however great needs.

Reference [8] suggested the provision of adequate facilities and equipment as a pre-requisite to successful execution of mass sports programmes in developing countries. Furthermore, comprehensive publicity is considered a vital step in the regular participation in sports and related activities

[7]. Family members, peers and friends were said to be impediment to female sports. In some cases however, these may wield positive influence. The facts that a number of lecturers in the institution discourage students from sports practices and competitions are unfortunate. This is, however, are not new [1]. Reported that students athletes were discouraged by some of the academic staff who considered that the sole purpose of the University students who to attain academic excellence. Some of such lecturers do everything possible to frustrate and discourage the efforts of students who showed interest in sport especially at competition level. One way by which they did this was to schedule lecturers and test at periods already fixed for sports contrary to the policy of institution.

Reference [6] some lecturers advise their students strongly to face studies and shun sports if they want to succeed. Some academicians regard sports as mere extracurricular activities that have little or nothing to contribute to students' academic excellence; hence, some lecturers do not regard it as a component of the educational experiences offered to the students [2].

Some religions such as Islam, do not favour female participation in sport as women should not be exposed and cannot perform in open places like sports field. Religion in some cases state the mode of dressing which is not in consonance with what is needed for efficient sport performance. It was also identified that the rigidity in the admission policy of the institution was so much that Sportswomen were not given any preferential treatment. This is not so in other countries particularly the developed ones.

Admission to higher institutions in Nigeria has to rigid rules so much that a lot of talented Sportswomen are refused admission, whereas they get these plus scholarships in America, British and German Universities. These rejected athletes were always later invited for international competitions involving Nigerians [7]. Some Nigerians athletes that were refused admission in Universities here because they were 'not qualified' studied abroad and returned to lecture in the Universities that had earlier rejected them.

IV. RECOMMENDATIONS

Sufficient fund should be provided by the government for Sports so that all other factors such qualified and adequate number of personnel, facilities, equipments and supplies can also be provided too.

The lecturers that discourage Sportswomen should be educated on the need for students to participate in sports. The Sports Director should work closely with the management to remove all impediments to female Sports management and participation. Adequate incentives should be provided in order to have the best participation from the students.

The institutions should add to whatever the government provides with Sports fee to be paid by students as well as donations. The institution should generate fund for Sports development.

The government and the management of the institutions should endeavour to place Sport appropriately. It should be a

part of an academic system rather than an unrecognized appendage or extra-curricular activity.

At least a unit course in Physical Education and Sports should be made a condition for graduation in the Colleges.

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